

CROSS-ANALYSIS OF JEWELLERY TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Pirnazarova Nargiza Chorshanbiyevna

An English teacher at secondary school No.13,

Termez city, Surkandarya Region

A master's student at the Faculty of Foreign

Languages and Literature of TISU

Annotation:

This article provides information related to jewelry terms and types of jewelry available in English and Uzbek languages. Jewelry has always been a favorite of women in all countries. The terms related to jewelry in two languages are introduced and compared.

Keywords: Jewelry terms, English and Uzbek jewels, gems, gemstones. precious stones

Аннотация:

В данной статье представлена информация о ювелирных терминах и видах ювелирных изделий, доступных на английском и узбекском языках. Ювелирные изделия всегда были фаворитом женщин во всех странах. Вводятся и сравниваются термины, относящиеся к ювелирным изделиям в двух языках.

Ключевые слова: Ювелирные термины, английские и узбекские драгоценности, драгоценные камни, драгоценные камни. драгоценные камни

Introduction

In the following article, the definitions of women's clothes decorations are given and explored in terms of size that serve to make them more attractive. With the passage of time, over centuries jewelry has enriched and polished each other. It is explained that jewelry that has not lost its value is called differently in two languages. A comprehensive understanding of jewelry is given and explained.

Analysis of literature and methodology

Uzbek language lexicology is rich in jewelry definitions which are quite different from English. But English lexicology is also affluent with diverse jewelry-

related words. The names of jewelry are different in different places of Uzbekistan and in most cases they are named after body parts.

English language lexicology has a diverse range of jewelry words and some of them are given below:

A **PARURE** means a set of jewelry in French. It includes a necklace, earring brooch, bracelet, diadem, and other accessories.

JEWELS - the word alludes to precious stones like rubies, emeralds, and diamonds which are used in making jewelry items.

FALLALERY is an old-fashioned word that is used for jewels, means jewelry, and means inexpensive ornament. Clothes that are worn at Halloween can be examples of fallal jewelry;

BESPOKE JEWELRY is made for the specific request of customers. Bespoke jewelry can be made from precious stones like emeralds, rubies, sapphires, and other stones for reminding special days. For this reason, it can be memorable and people give them to somebody as a gift;

BAUBLE is a kind of jewelry that is showy, small, and cheap; Christmas trees are usually decorated with baubles;

GEMSTONES are precious stones and are considered the most beautiful minerals with an elegant appearance. Gemstones are an invaluable gift of nature and have attracted humankind from ancient times

KNICK-KNACK is also jewelry related word that is small and worthless objects usually used to decorate a room.

BIJOUTERIE is a collection of ornaments and trinkets. The word bijou comes from French. People wear it on their bodies or clothes.

BLING-BLING is a type of jewelry that is expensive and usually used for clothes to attract attention.

BANGLE is an ornament worn around the arm and ankle. The word bangle is a Hindi word and means colored glass bracelet.

CAMEO an oval shape of jewelry that contains a portrait which is carved into it.

ZIRCON – the word comes from the Persian ‘zargun’ which means ‘gold-colored; It looks like a diamond and it is a natural gemstone.

RING is a circular-shaped metal made of both cheap and expensive types, worn on a finger as an ornament;

EARRING an ornament for the ear ;

HOOP EARRING a circular-shaped metal that can be opened to pass through an ear piercing;

NECKLACE this kind of jewelry is worn around the neck, chain, or string of beads ;

Uzbek jewelry has an ancient history. Our wise people said that “If there is only one woman on earth there is a job for jewelers” Uzbek jewelry dates back to the primitive community. It can be seen from the archaeological finds that jewelry is one of the oldest crafts. Jewelry items were made of stones, glass, and bones in the earliest century. Lion and frog-shaped jewelry were found in the territory of Khorezm. During that period jewelry was mainly used for animals birds, fish, and mythical creatures. People thought that they would protect them from different kinds of calamities. The shape and decoration of ornaments date back to earlier centuries. If we speak about Uzbek jewelry we should mention that they are diverse and endless. The names of them also don't repeat each other. All of them are particularly made for every part of the body. There are such kinds of jewelry that are mainly for the head, forehead, temples, long hair ear, neck, chest, armpits, waist, legs, and nose. For example:

TAXYADUZI - women wear it on their heads. It is made of colorful stones and glass;

ZIRAK - It is usually worn through the ear and made of precious and unprecious metals;

BODOMOY - This kind of ornament is special for temples;

TUMOR ,SHAVKALA, SOCHPOPUK, GAJAK, BUTUNTIRNOQ, KUSH, DUO – are worn on chest;

ARAVAK - is made for the nose;

BUYINTUMOR is worn by women on their necks;

KAMAR, PESHXALTA, and KALITBOG'I are for their waist;

BILAKUZUK - circle-shaped ornament for hand ;

Uzbek language lexicology is also rich in a variety of jewelry terms which passed from generation to generation over centuries and have been used by people to make their clothes more attractive. The earliest jewelry antecedes to the 17th century BC and was found near the source of the Chirchik River. Amu Darya's treasure was also unique to Bactrian jewelers. Uzbek women have always been worn, unlike jewelry items from ancient times. Our great-grandmothers had utilized

adornments that have been considered a part of the Uzbek people's culture. And one thing should be mentioned that there is a proverb among Uzbek people. “ Do not show your mother to your father without jewelry....”

Some glorious and shining jewelry terms will be introduced to your attention:

ZARGAR – the word means a person who makes jewelry from metal. They are jewelry masters.

TILLIYA-KOSH the crown of the bride. It is usually made from gold or gilding. It was a headgear.

MARDZHON – a necklace that is made from the coral bunch which was adored by Uzbek women.

ZEBIGUARDON -zebiguardon was placed at the center of the Necklace and was made from precious stones.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that the lexicology of the English and Uzbek language has a lot of modern and ancient words typical of jewelry, and they serve to enrich the language.

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